

Pharmaceuticals in water: a bibliometric review of removal technologies, research trends, and socioeconomic factors (2000-2025)

Fármacos na água: uma revisão bibliométrica de tecnologias de remoção, tendências de pesquisa e fatores socioeconômicos (2000-2025)

Productos farmacéuticos en el agua: una revisión bibliométrica de tecnologías de eliminación, tendencias de investigación y factores socioeconómicos (2000-2025)

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Daiane Francisca do N. Silva

Master in Energy and Nuclear Technologies
Institution: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE)
Address: Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil
E-mail: daiane.francisca@ufpe.br

Jean Firmino Cardoso

Bachelor in Civil Engineering
Institution: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE)
Address: Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil
E-mail: jean.firmino@ufpe.br

Daniel Milian Pérez

Doctor in Energy and Nuclear Technologies
Institution: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE)
Address: Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil
E-mail: daniel.milian@ufpe.br

Abel Gámez Rodríguez

Doctor in Energy and Nuclear Technologies
Institution: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE)
Address: Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil
E-mail: abel.rodriguez@ufpe.br

Yaiel Ge Proenza

Doctor in Chemistry

Institution: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE)

Address: Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil

E-mail: yaiel.geproenza@ufpe.br

Antonio Celso Dantas Antonino

Doctor in Soil Physics

Institution: Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE)

Address: Recife, Pernambuco, Brazil

E-mail: antonio.antonino@ufpe.br

ABSTRACT

Pharmaceutical contamination in aquatic environments is a growing global concern due to its ecological and public health implications. These compounds, often resistant to conventional treatments, originate from domestic, hospital, and industrial effluents and persist in water bodies. This study presents a bibliometric review of scientific publications from 2000 to 2025, aiming to examine the relationship between pharmaceutical pollution, socioeconomic conditions, and remediation technologies. Data were collected from Scopus and Web of Science using the keywords “removal AND pharmaceuticals AND water”. Duplicate records were removed, and the final dataset was processed using a custom Python script to generate bibliometric visualizations. A three-stage filtering process was applied to identify relevant studies, characterize methodologies, and select articles for full reading. Results show a consistent increase in scientific output over the years, with a notable concentration of research in China, the United States, and Brazil. Adsorption was identified as the most explored technique, often employing activated carbon, biochar, and nanomaterials. Funding trends peaked in 2024, with a slight drop in 2025 due to incomplete data. The findings indicate increasing global engagement with pharmaceutical removal, emphasizing the role of research in addressing both environmental and social inequalities. This review highlights the need for scalable, efficient, and context-sensitive treatment solutions.

Keywords: Water Contamination. Pharmaceutical Pollution. Socioeconomic Conditions. Removal Technologies. Bibliometric Analysis. Adsorption.

RESUMO

A contaminação por fármacos em ambientes aquáticos é uma preocupação crescente devido aos riscos que representa à saúde pública e ao equilíbrio ecológico. Esses compostos, frequentemente recalcitrantes aos tratamentos convencionais, são introduzidos nas águas por esgotos domésticos, hospitalares e industriais. Este estudo apresenta uma revisão bibliométrica da produção científica entre 2000 e 2025, com o objetivo de investigar a relação entre a poluição por fármacos, as condições socioeconômicas e as tecnologias de remediação empregadas. Foram utilizados dados das bases Scopus e Web of Science com os termos “removal AND pharmaceuticals AND water”. Após a remoção de

duplicatas, os dados foram processados por meio de um script desenvolvido em Python. A análise foi conduzida em três etapas: elegibilidade, caracterização e leitura completa. Os resultados revelam crescimento consistente da produção científica, com destaque para China, Estados Unidos e Brasil. A adsorção foi a técnica mais estudada, com uso recorrente de carvão ativado, biocarvão e nanomateriais. O financiamento à pesquisa apresentou pico em 2024, com queda aparente em 2025 devido a dados ainda parciais. Conclui-se que há um engajamento crescente na busca por soluções eficazes, escaláveis e adaptadas aos diferentes contextos socioeconômicos, reforçando o papel da ciência na mitigação de desigualdades ambientais.

Palavras-chave: Contaminação da Água. Poluição por Fármacos. Condições Socioeconômicas. Tecnologias de Remoção. Análise Bibliométrica. Adsorção.

RESUMEN

La contaminación por fármacos en entornos acuáticos representa un problema ambiental y sanitario en expansión. Estos compuestos, difíciles de eliminar mediante tratamientos convencionales, provienen de descargas domésticas, hospitalarias e industriales, permaneciendo en cuerpos de agua. Este estudio ofrece una revisión bibliométrica de publicaciones científicas entre 2000 y 2025, con el objetivo de analizar la relación entre la contaminación farmacéutica, las condiciones socioeconómicas y las tecnologías de remediación utilizadas. Se recolectaron datos de las bases Scopus y Web of Science mediante la búsqueda “removal AND pharmaceuticals AND water”. Tras eliminar duplicados, los datos fueron procesados mediante un script personalizado en Python. La selección de artículos se realizó en tres fases: análisis de elegibilidad, caracterización y lectura completa. Los resultados muestran un crecimiento constante en la producción científica, destacando China, Estados Unidos y Brasil como principales productores. La técnica más investigada fue la adsorción, utilizando carbón activado, biochar y nanomateriales. La financiación alcanzó su punto máximo en 2024, con un descenso en 2025 atribuible a datos incompletos. El estudio revela un compromiso creciente con la remediación de contaminantes farmacéuticos, subrayando la importancia de desarrollar soluciones efectivas, accesibles y adaptadas a distintas realidades sociales.

Palabras clave: Contaminación del Agua. Polución Farmacéutica. Condiciones Socioeconómicas. Tecnologías de Eliminación. Análisis Bibliométrico. Adsorción.

1 INTRODUCTION

The contamination of water resources by pharmaceutical compounds, classified as part of the broader group of emerging contaminants, has become a pressing global concern due to its potential impacts on both environmental

integrity and public health. These substances, commonly referred to as pharmaceutical and personal care products (PPCPs), include a wide range of bioactive molecules such as antibiotics, analgesics, hormones, and antidepressants (LETSOALO *et al.*, 2023). Their release into aquatic ecosystems occurs through several pathways, including discharges from Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs), effluents from chemical and pharmaceutical industries (CPI), inappropriate product usage and disposal, domestic and industrial activities, surface runoff and leaching, as well as illegal discharges and human activities (Anliker *et al.*, 2022; Cangola; Abagale; Cobbina, 2024; Delgado *et al.*, 2023; Ślósarczyk; Wolny; Witkowski, 2025).

Pharmaceuticals are particularly problematic because they are often designed to be biologically active and persistent. Their physicochemical properties—such as high solubility and resistance to biodegradation—facilitate their mobility and persistence in aquatic environments (Battaglin *et al.*, 2018). Studies have shown that even low concentrations of pharmaceuticals can induce a variety of adverse effects on aquatic organisms, including behavioral changes, endocrine disruption, oxidative stress, and alterations in reproductive and physiological processes (Anliker *et al.*, 2022; Battaglin *et al.*, 2018; Delgado *et al.*, 2023). The presence of antibiotics in water bodies contributes to the emergence and spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, which poses a severe threat to global public health (Battaglin *et al.*, 2018; Cangola; Abagale; Cobbina, 2024; Ślósarczyk; Wolny; Witkowski, 2025). In addition, some pharmaceuticals can bioaccumulate in aquatic organisms and, through the food chain, reach higher concentrations in predators, including humans (Battaglin *et al.*, 2018; Delgado *et al.*, 2023; Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023).

Given the limitations of conventional wastewater treatment processes in effectively removing these micropollutants, the need for advanced remediation technologies has become increasingly evident. In recent years, significant scientific efforts have been directed toward identifying innovative materials and methods capable of mitigating the risks associated with pharmaceutical contamination in water (Ahmad *et al.*, 2025; Borah *et al.*, 2025; Choudhury *et al.*, 2025; Dong *et al.*, 2025; Issaka; Danso-Boateng; Baffoe, 2024; Silva *et al.*, 2018;

Sirés; Brillas, 2012). However, despite the growing body of research on this topic, gaps remain regarding the relationship between the geographic distribution of contamination, local socioeconomic conditions, and the adoption of specific remediation technologies. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing strategies that are not only technically effective but also socially and economically viable (Delgado *et al.*, 2023; Cangola; Abagale; Cobbina, 2024; Vinther *et al.*, 2025).

In response to these gaps, this study presents a bibliometric review of publications from 2000 to 2025 that address the removal of pharmaceuticals from water, with a specific focus on identifying trends in research output, leading countries and institutions, most studied contaminants, frequently used reactive materials, and the interplay between scientific productivity and socioeconomic indicators.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Water contamination by synthetic organic compounds presents numerous challenges for environmental protection and public health. Among these compounds are industrial chemicals, pesticides, and pharmaceutical residues, many of which are not efficiently removed by conventional WWTPs. The underestimation of industrial pollution, especially from synthetic organic compounds, and the urgent need for innovative treatment solutions as alternatives to energy-inefficient wastewater incineration underscore the gravity of the problem. Technologies such as fluorescence spectroscopy still face difficulties in quantifying contaminants due to interference from fluorescent organic matter (Anliker *et al.*, 2022; Vinther *et al.*, 2025). Additionally, promising methods like the use of BioMnOx for micropollutant removal still require thorough investigation at realistic concentrations and under in situ conditions (Furgal; Meyer; Bester, 2014). Significant knowledge gaps persist, including the lack of a centralized database of contaminant absorbance and fluorescence properties (Vinther *et al.*, 2025). Among emerging contaminants, pharmaceuticals have received increasing attention in recent years. Beyond their environmental

occurrence and effects—already discussed in the introduction—attention has shifted toward improving detection and treatment technologies specific to these compounds.

Recent innovations in the identification of pharmaceuticals in water encompass advanced analytical techniques and the development of high-sensitivity biosensors. Untargeted High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) enables the identification of unforeseen compounds, while fluorescence spectroscopy offers a cost-effective alternative for characterizing dissolved organic matter (Anliker *et al.*, 2022; Vinther *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, electrochemical and optical biosensors, utilizing aptamers and metallic nanoparticles, facilitate the selective detection of various pharmaceuticals at low concentrations (Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023).

Beyond detection, technological hurdles persist in the development of effective treatment methods for pharmaceutical contaminants. Nanocellulose faces problems with self-aggregation and difficulties in its large-scale manufacturing and modification (Nordin *et al.*, 2024), while nanofiltration membranes and nanomaterials are still under development and exhibit limitations such as fouling and high costs (Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023). Modeling photocatalysis and optimizing low-cost adsorbents, like powdered activated carbon (PAC), also require further investigation (Campinas *et al.*, 2021; Durán-Álvarez *et al.*, 2024; Mueses *et al.*, 2021).

Among the available technologies for the removal of pharmaceutical compounds from water, adsorption has gained prominence, offering simplicity, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness. It allows for the use of diverse materials such as activated carbon, biochar, nano-adsorbents, zeolites, and other low-cost options (Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023; Nordin *et al.*, 2024; Priyan V; Narayanasamy, 2022). While other techniques like membranes, advanced oxidation processes, biological and chemical treatments, and piezocatalysis are also employed, adsorption's versatility and efficacy make it one of the most promising approaches for remediating emerging contaminants (Abdullah *et al.*, 2024; Delgado *et al.*, 2023; Demiti *et al.*, 2025; Mueses *et al.*, 2021). Current research emphasizes the need for alternative remediation techniques with high selectivity

and adsorption affinity, aiming to overcome the limitations of conventional technologies (Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023). Key areas of focus include the application of nanoadsorbents and the mathematical modeling of solar photocatalytic reactors to optimize large-scale treatment (Mueses *et al.*, 2021; Priyan V; Narayanasamy, 2022).

Focusing specifically on the removal of pharmaceuticals from water, adsorption proves to be an efficient technique, with increasing attention on nanocellulose-based adsorbents and other nanomaterials (Furgal; Meyer; Bester, 2014; Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023; Mueses *et al.*, 2021). Carbon nanotubes, graphene oxide, and magnetic nanocomposites are also being explored, despite ongoing challenges related to their cost and potential toxicity (Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs), membrane technologies, biotransformations, and heterogeneous photocatalysis are employed to optimize the removal of these persistent organic pollutants (Demiti *et al.*, 2025; Durán-Álvarez *et al.*, 2024; Letsoalo *et al.*, 2023).

Although considerable scientific progress has been made, several critical aspects remain understudied. Comprehensive data on the occurrence and risks of PPCPs in aquatic systems are still limited (Cangola; Abagale; Cobbina, 2024). The concentrations and impacts of veterinary pharmaceuticals, in particular, are poorly understood, highlighting a crucial area for future investigation (Delgado *et al.*, 2023). This theoretical overview highlights the complexity of pharmaceutical contamination in water matrices and frames the rationale for conducting a bibliometric review. This study aims to explore trends in remediation technologies and analyze the influence of socioeconomic conditions on scientific output between 2000 and 2025.

3 METHODOLOGY

This bibliometric review investigates the interrelation between pharmaceutical contamination in water resources, the adoption of remediation technologies, and local socioeconomic conditions. Specifically, it investigates (i) the most prevalent pharmaceuticals in aquatic environments, (ii) the reactive materials most

employed for their removal, (iii) the evolution of research output and recent technological advances, and (iv) the geographic and institutional distribution of scientific contributions. Furthermore, it seeks to understand how local socioeconomic conditions relate to the development and application of remediation strategies.

The research encompassed works published between the years 2000 and March 2025, covering virtually the entire development concerning the application of reactive materials in the removal of contaminants from water resources. The inclusion of data up to March 2025 ensures a current overview of recent trends, although readers should note that the 2025 dataset is partial and may not represent the full year's output. Scientific data were collected from the Scopus and Web of Science platforms using the combined search terms: “removal AND pharmaceuticals AND water”. The query was unrestricted with respect to language or document type, ensuring broad coverage.

Basic information including titles, publication years, authors, abstracts, keywords, citations, and affiliations were exported from the databases and processed using Python. A Python script was developed to perform the bibliometric analysis, covering the entire workflow from data cleaning to results export. Essential libraries such as pandas and matplotlib were employed for data manipulation and visualization. This stage included removal of duplicate entries, chronological organization, data preprocessing, analysis of geographical affiliations, funding sources, and temporal trends. The script generated word clouds, distribution charts, and semantic networks, with results exported in formats like PNG and Excel for enhanced interpretability.

Subsequently, the documents were analyzed in three stages: (1) titles and abstracts were read to determine whether each work met the eligibility criteria. In this stage, a bibliometric analysis was also performed on the retrieved documents to identify research trends and the countries most engaged with the subject. This analysis further allowed an exploration of the economic implications associated with concerns over the preservation and remediation of water resources; (2) titles, abstracts, keywords, and methodology sections were examined to characterize each document in terms of contaminant removal strategy, country of study, type of study, and the specific water matrix analyzed; (3) finally, a selection of

documents was chosen for full reading. This selection included only those studies that addressed strategies for removing pharmaceuticals from water resources using reactive materials. Figure 1 presents the flowchart outlining this process, along with the eligibility criteria applied in the research.

Figure 1. Flow diagram illustrating the sequential selection process of the documents analyzed.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Following the general bibliometric analysis, a more targeted filtering process was conducted to select articles whose titles contained keywords semantically aligned with the structure “pharmaceutical + water + removal”. Consequently, from the initial pool of 3,387 articles encompassed within the bibliometric review, 95 were selected for full-text analysis aimed at constructing a timeline of key technological and methodological developments.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the main findings of the bibliometric review, organized into two complementary parts. First, we examine the evolution of scientific production over the 2000–2025 period, highlighting geographic distribution, funding sources, institutional engagement, and keyword dynamics. This quantitative overview provides insight into the global research landscape and its driving forces. In the second part, we synthesize the key advances in contaminant identification and pharmaceutical removal strategies, establishing a timeline of

technological developments and scientific focus areas. Together, these analyses allow for a comprehensive understanding of how research on pharmaceutical pollutants in water has progressed, and how it relates to broader socioeconomic and environmental challenges.

4.1 BIBLIOMETRIC REVIEW

Of the articles selected for this research, the robust growth in scientific output observed throughout the analyzed period (Figure 2) indicates a dynamic and rapidly expanding area of research. The steady rise in publications addressing pharmaceutical contaminant removal from water points to not only an increase in research funding and institutional support, but also the mobilization of a larger scientific community and the strengthening of international collaboration networks.

Figure 2. Trends in publications related to pharmaceuticals removal between 2000 and 2025.

Source: Prepared by the authors

Notably, the acceleration witnessed in the last decade raises pertinent questions regarding the driving forces behind this trend. Specific technological advancements within the remediation technologies, the introduction of innovative analytical methods, the diversification of funding mechanisms, and the growing societal awareness of water pollution risks are likely among the key contributing

factors. Investigating the correlations between significant events and publication peaks could yield valuable insights into the broader dynamics shaping scientific engagement in this critical environmental domain.

An analysis of agency-funded publications over the past 25 years (Figure 3) reveals a marked and consistent increase in research supported by funding agencies, culminating in a peak of 341 documents in 2024. The three-year moving average further reinforces this upward trajectory, reflecting the consolidation of the field and the growing institutional investment in pharmaceutical contaminant removal. The apparent drop in 2025 is not indicative of a decline in interest or funding, but rather a consequence of partial data availability, limited to the first quarter of the year. Overall, the trend underscores a significant rise in financial support and international collaboration in this area of research.

Figure 3. Trends in publications on pharmaceuticals removal supported by funding agencies between 2000 and 2025.

Source: Prepared by the authors

The next analysis focused on identifying the main funding agencies supporting research in this field (Figure 4). The results reveal a clear dominance by Chinese and European institutions, with the National Natural Science Foundation of China emerging as the leading sponsor, followed by European bodies such as the European Regional Development Fund and the European Commission. This concentration of financial support highlights the pivotal role of

national and supranational agencies in advancing pharmaceutical removal technologies. Notably, Brazilian funding agencies also appear among the top five, indicating substantial investment, despite facing broader socioeconomic constraints.

Figure 4. The top 20 funding agencies supporting research on pharmaceutical removal from water resources between 2000 and 2025.

Source: Prepared by the authors

When correlating this information with the number of publications by country (Figure 5), it is observable that despite not leading in the frequency of agency-funded publications, the United States leads in the total number of articles published on the topic. This pattern may reflect the structural characteristics of the U.S. research ecosystem, where a significant portion of scientific output is supported by institutional funds, philanthropic foundations, or internal university resources that are not always explicitly cited in publications. Additionally, differences in editorial policies and funding disclosure requirements may contribute to the underreporting of financial support in U.S.-based studies. Following the United States, China ranks second in the number of publications, succeeded by India, Spain, Germany, Brazil, France and United Kingdom.

Figure 5. Number of Publications by Country.

Source: Prepared by the authors

To better understand the relationship between scientific productivity and structural conditions in each country, we conducted a comparison that combines research output with key indicators of water quality, human development, and economic performance (Table 1). This approach enables a more holistic interpretation of the drivers behind national engagement in pharmaceutical removal from water resources.

Table 1. Comparative indicators of countries with the highest scientific output on pharmaceutical removal from water (2000–2025), including EPI drinking water quality score (EPI 2024), Human Development Index (HDI), and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita.

Country	Publications	EPI rank	EPI score	HDI (category)	GDP per capita
United States	470	1	100.00	0.927 (Very high)	\$72,000.00
Germany	140	5	98.10	0.954 (Very high)	\$69,756.66
United Kingdom	112	9	97.00	0.940 (Very high)	\$52,622.00
Spain	244	16	93.60	0.905 (Very high)	\$52,327.61
France	127	28	85.30	0.910 (Very high)	\$58,826.05
China	364	30	76.50	0.788 (High)	\$25,962.81
Brazil	160	63	60.60	0.760 (High)	\$19,996.65
India	280	136	25.80	0.644 (Medium)	\$9,387.60

Source: Prepared by the authors

Notably, the United States, Germany and United Kingdom rank among the top 10 countries worldwide in terms of water quality (EPI 2024) (Water Quality by Country 2025, 2025; Environmental Performance Index, 2025) and also lead in total publication volume. These nations also exhibit very high Human Development Index (HDI) (WISE Metrics – Beyond-GDP, 2025) scores and high GDP per capita (GDP per capita, 2025), reflecting a context in which robust

scientific production is aligned with strong infrastructure, institutional capacity, and environmental governance.

China, in contrast, demonstrates a remarkable volume of scientific output despite presenting lower EPI scores and only a “high” HDI, paired with a moderate GDP per capita. This suggests that research intensity in pharmaceutical removal is not strictly dependent on economic wealth or water quality performance, but may instead be driven by population size, environmental urgency, and strong state-led investment in science and technology. A similar pattern is observed in Brazil, which, although lagging in water quality (EPI score of 60.6) and GDP per capita when compared to developed nations, maintains a high level of research activity. Brazil’s inclusion among the top funding countries indicates a deliberate national policy orientation toward environmental research and innovation, even under budgetary constraints.

In India, the lowest EPI score among the countries analyzed (25.8) is accompanied by a medium HDI rating and low GDP per capita. Yet, the country exhibits significant scientific engagement in pharmaceutical removal. This may reflect urgent public health challenges, combined with governmental or international support aimed at improving water safety. The data suggest that acute environmental stress can serve as a catalyst for scientific mobilization, even in the absence of strong economic indicators.

Finally, European Union countries such as France, Spain, and Germany display a more consistent profile: high scores across all indicators (EPI, HDI, GDP) along with solid research output. The United Kingdom, although no longer a member of the EU, also exhibits a similarly strong performance. These cases reflect long-standing commitments to both environmental quality and investment in science, often underpinned by robust national policies and, in the case of EU members, collaborative funding mechanisms at the European level.

In summary, scientific productivity in the field of pharmaceutical pollution removal appears to be shaped by complex intersections of environmental urgency, development status, and institutional capacity. High levels of research output are not limited to economically privileged nations; rather, they frequently emerge in contexts where pressing environmental challenges demand immediate

and sustained scientific responses, often reflected in national or regional policy priorities.

Concluding the analyses on the temporal and geographic distribution of scientific output, we also examined how knowledge is disseminated within the field through different types of scientific documents. Figure 6 provides a comprehensive look at this dimension, revealing that research articles are by far the predominant vehicle for publishing original findings, showing a robust and sustained growth over the years. While review papers also increased in frequency, reflecting the growing need for synthesis and consolidation of knowledge, they did so with greater year-to-year variability. Altogether, these results highlight a maturing and increasingly diversified scientific field, with research articles firmly leading the way in terms of knowledge production and dissemination.

Figure 6. Temporal evolution of scientific publication types related to pharmaceutical removal from water (2000–2025).

Source: Prepared by the authors

4.2 CONTAMINANT IDENTIFICATION AND REMOVAL: KEY ADVANCES FROM 2000 TO 2025

To provide a structured understanding of the scientific advances in the field, this section presents a detailed chronological review of the literature on the

remediation of emerging contaminants, with a specific focus on pharmaceuticals in water resources. The aim is to map the evolution of treatment strategies, technological innovations, and research priorities from 2000 to 2025, highlighting key milestones and transitions in scientific approaches to pharmaceutical pollution. The review is organized into subperiods that reflect distinct stages in the field's development: from early detection and problem recognition (2000–2005), through the emergence of advanced technologies and source control initiatives (2006–2010), to the consolidation of multi-barrier strategies and nanotechnologies (2011–2015), the diversification of materials and processes (2016–2020), and, finally, the recent trend towards integrated, multifunctional treatment systems (2021–2025).

Between 2000 and 2005, significant progress was made in understanding the occurrence, fate, and treatment of emerging contaminants, with particular emphasis on pharmaceuticals in water sources (O. A. H. Jones *et al.*, 2005; Lopez *et al.*, 2003; Ternes *et al.*, 2002; Matamoros *et al.*, 2005). Numerous reviews and studies documented the widespread detection of these substances and underscored the limited efficacy of conventional wastewater treatment processes (Gross *et al.*, 2004; Lam *et al.*, 2004; Rooklidge *et al.*, 2005). Persistent contaminants such as iodinated radiocontrast media were found in both U.S. and German treatment facilities, showing resistance to conventional degradation pathways (Drewes *et al.*, 2001; Ternes *et al.*, 2002; O. A. H. Jones *et al.*, 2005).

Investigations into antibiotic biodegradability and resistance highlighted concerns related to urban effluents (Bound & Voulvoulis, 2005; Young *et al.*, 2014), while studies on filter systems reported varying removal efficiencies for compounds such as sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim, and lincomycin (Rooklidge *et al.*, 2005). Other contaminants of interest included triclosan, fluoroquinolones, APEMs, and estrogens (Gross *et al.*, 2004; Ternes *et al.*, 2002; Matamoros *et al.*, 2005).

Pharmaceuticals like carbamazepine, diclofenac, ibuprofen, and clofibrac acid were frequently studied due to their persistence in aquatic systems and resistance to removal (Bound & Voulvoulis, 2005; O. A. H. Jones *et al.*, 2005; Lam

et al., 2004; Ternes *et al.*, 2002). Caffeine was recognized as an anthropogenic indicator of contamination (Ternes *et al.*, 2002; O. A. H. Jones *et al.*, 2005). Slow sand and roughing filters showed compound-specific performance, with adsorption to filter media playing a key role in removal mechanisms (Rooklidge *et al.*, 2005).

As conventional treatments proved inadequate for many compounds, attention shifted to advanced technologies. Membrane processes such as nanofiltration and reverse osmosis demonstrated high removal efficiencies for pharmaceuticals and radiocontrast agents (Vedavyasan, 2000; Drewes *et al.*, 2001). UV-based oxidation processes (e.g., UV/H₂O₂) showed promise for degrading pharmaceutical intermediates, especially in waters with low turbidity (Lopez *et al.*, 2003; Lam *et al.*, 2004). Granular activated carbon adsorption also proved effective, particularly for compounds like bezafibrate, carbamazepine, and diclofenac (Ternes *et al.*, 2002; Young *et al.*, 2014).

Natural attenuation processes were extensively evaluated. Studies of riverine transport, artificial recharge, and constructed wetlands revealed partial removal and transformation of various contaminants, dependent on redox conditions and compound characteristics (Gross *et al.*, 2004; Drewes *et al.*, 2001; Matamoros *et al.*, 2005). Riverbank filtration and reclaimed water irrigation were explored as mitigation strategies (O. A. H. Jones *et al.*, 2005; Young *et al.*, 2014).

From the years 2006 to 2010, the evolution from detection-focused studies to advanced treatment development and source control initiatives reflects a growing understanding of the complexity of micropollutant removal. A holistic, integrated approach remains essential for addressing these persistent environmental challenges.

Growing awareness of micropollutants such as pharmaceuticals, endocrine disruptors, and PPCPs in aquatic environments has led to increased research efforts (Broséus *et al.*, 2009; Chelliapan *et al.*, 2006; Cuerda-Correa *et al.*, 2010; Gros *et al.*, 2007; Heberer *et al.*, 2008; Püttmann *et al.*, 2008; Whelehan *et al.*, 2010). Initial studies primarily addressed their occurrence and quantification in wastewater and surface waters, revealing the limited removal capacity of conventional WWTPs (Gros *et al.*, 2007). Although acute toxicity to aquatic

organisms was generally low, concerns about chronic toxicity and mixture effects persisted (Gros *et al.*, 2007).

Subsequent research focused on evaluating treatment technologies. Biological processes such as activated sludge showed substance-specific removal efficiencies, often improved by increasing sludge retention time (SRT), though compounds like carbamazepine remained resistant (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008; White *et al.*, 2006; Gros *et al.*, 2007). Membrane bioreactors (MBRs) offered improved operational control but did not consistently outperform conventional treatments for most micropollutants (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008; Dordio *et al.*, 2009). Anaerobic treatment was also explored under various operational conditions (Chelliapan *et al.*, 2006).

Among physicochemical methods, adsorption using activated carbon proved particularly effective and has been implemented in both wastewater and drinking water contexts (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008; White *et al.*, 2006). Powdered activated carbon (PAC) reduced pharmaceutical loads by up to 80%, albeit with higher operational costs and potential impacts on sludge management (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008). Alternative adsorbents such as carbon black have been assessed for NSAIDs under different pH and temperature conditions (Cuerda-Correa *et al.*, 2010).

Oxidation techniques, especially ozonation and AOPs, demonstrated high degradation efficiency for various PPCPs but were limited by high costs and the risk of by-product formation (Broséus *et al.*, 2009; Kim *et al.*, 2009; Püttmann *et al.*, 2008; Wintgens *et al.*, 2008). Membrane technologies, including nanofiltration (NF) and reverse osmosis (RO), showed high rejection rates for a wide spectrum of emerging contaminants (White *et al.*, 2006; Wintgens *et al.*, 2008). Natural and semi-natural systems such as bank filtration and constructed wetlands also showed selective effectiveness, particularly in removing antimicrobial residues and specific metabolites like clofibric acid (Heberer *et al.*, 2008; Dordio *et al.*, 2009).

Around the year 2008, a consensus had formed around the necessity of multi-barrier strategies combining different treatment technologies to ensure effective removal of diverse micropollutants (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008; Wintgens *et al.*,

2008). In drinking water treatment, the integration of activated carbon and ozonation is often recommended, especially when source waters are vulnerable to contamination (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008).

Additionally, source control measures have been proposed to reduce contaminant input at its origin. These include substance flow separation (e.g., wastewater from hospitals), localized treatment systems, and decentralized sanitation concepts such as “No-Mix-Toilets” for segregating different wastewater streams (Püttmann *et al.*, 2008). Such strategies may offer more sustainable and cost-effective solutions for managing high-risk compounds than end-of-pipe treatments alone.

From 2011 onwards, the field saw a shift from conventional methods to advanced oxidation, adsorption, biological, and membrane-based technologies for more effective PPCPs removal. Studies explored electrochemical methods like electrocoagulation, anodic oxidation (using BDD anodes), and electro-Fenton for effective degradation of pharmaceuticals (Sirés & Brillas, 2012). Sulfate radical-based AOTs using PMS and persulfate were also developed as alternatives to hydroxyl radical-based processes (Nfodzo & Choi, 2011). Reverse osmosis showed high removal efficiency (Boleda *et al.*, 2011).

Emerging contaminants such as PPCPs in surface and groundwater have raised increasing concern due to their persistence and the limited efficacy of conventional treatment methods (Dolar *et al.*, 2012; Ibáñez *et al.*, 2013; Moreira *et al.*, 2015; Nfodzo & Choi, 2011; Quesada-Peñate *et al.*, 2012). Biodegradation plays a critical role in preventing their accumulation (Kruglova *et al.*, 2014).

By 2012, catalytic wet air oxidation (CWAO) with activated carbon was proposed for paracetamol removal in a hybrid adsorption–oxidation system (Quesada-Peñate *et al.*, 2012). MBR–RO systems achieved >99% removal for many micropollutants (Dolar *et al.*, 2012; Nielsen *et al.*, 2013).

AOPs, including ozonation and H₂O₂/UV, were studied further, as were adsorption and methods like ultrasound, photocatalysis, and Fenton (Nasuhoglu *et al.*, 2012; Quesada-Peñate *et al.*, 2012). Pilot-scale studies in 2013 evaluated ozone-based AOPs for removing up to 60 contaminants (Ibáñez *et al.*, 2013). Polishing steps post-MBR included O₃, O₃+H₂O₂, PAC, and ClO₂, with PAC

showing strong performance (Nielsen *et al.*, 2013). Resin-based adsorption was also noted (Grimmett, 2013).

In 2014, biodegradation of pharmaceuticals in nitrifying sludge was investigated at low temperatures (Kruglova *et al.*, 2014), and removal efficiency was compared across treatment systems like MTP, STS, and wetlands (Du *et al.*, 2014).

Later studies reviewed MOFs as promising adsorbents (Hasan & Jhung, 2015), and nanomaterials (ZnO, TiO₂, Ag NPs, ZVI-modified biochar) were proposed for microbial control (Inyang & Dickenson, 2015). Aerobic Granular Sludge (AGS) proved effective for fluoxetine removal through adsorption/desorption mechanisms (Moreira *et al.*, 2015).

A broad review of 168 micropollutants showed variable removal in conventional plants, with some compounds like caffeine being well removed, while others like carbamazepine persisted. Post-treatment with ozonation and sand filtration was recommended (Margot *et al.*, 2015).

The literature from 2016–2020 reflects a growing focus on diverse removal strategies for emerging contaminants, combining adsorption, AOPs, biological treatments, and nanotechnology. The reviewed sources focus on removing emerging contaminants—including PPCPs, EDCs, and pesticides—such as antibiotics (e.g., amoxicillin, ciprofloxacin), analgesics (e.g., diclofenac, ibuprofen), and others like carbamazepine and triclosan (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017; Guo *et al.*, 2020; Mojiri *et al.*, 2020; Rasheed *et al.*, 2019; Silva *et al.*, 2018a, 2018b; Sophia A. & Lima, 2018; Ushavipinachandran *et al.*, 2020; Weng *et al.*, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2017).

Adsorption is widely studied using materials like activated carbon, biochar, MOFs, and magnetic or modified adsorbents (Rocha *et al.*, 2020; Silva *et al.*, 2018b; Sophia A. & Lima, 2018; Thiebault, 2020). Studies explore interactions, kinetics, and mechanisms such as electrostatic attraction (Rocha *et al.*, 2020). AOPs—Fenton, photo-Fenton, ozonation, photocatalysis, ultrasound—are frequently cited for degrading pharmaceuticals (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017; Mirzaei *et al.*, 2017; Monteoliva-García *et al.*, 2019; Tasca *et al.*, 2020; Tolboom *et al.*, 2019;

Zhu *et al.*, 2019). Ferrate(VI) and electrochemical methods are also discussed (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017; Feng *et al.*, 2018).

Biological treatments include constructed wetlands and membrane bioreactors (Santos *et al.*, 2019; Thiebault, 2020; Zaied *et al.*, 2020), along with anaerobic digestion (Ghattas *et al.*, 2017; Mojiri *et al.*, 2020). Other techniques include membrane filtration (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017; Monteoliva-García *et al.*, 2019), electrocoagulation (Tasca *et al.*, 2020; Zaied *et al.*, 2020), algae-based removal (Tolboom *et al.*, 2019), and nanomaterials like magnetic nanoparticles and supported Fe/Ni (Guo *et al.*, 2020; Rocha *et al.*, 2020; Ushavipinachandran *et al.*, 2020; Weng *et al.*, 2018).

In recent years (2021 onwards), emerging contaminants, particularly PPCPs, have been increasingly detected in the environment due to inadequate disposal from sources such as hospital sewage, domestic waste, and pharmaceutical effluents (Abbasi *et al.*, 2021). These compounds pose risks to human health, ecosystems, and can induce antibiotic resistance (Adeoye *et al.*, 2024; Fallah *et al.*, n.d.; Denora *et al.*, 2024; Masinga *et al.*, 2024; Moreno-Bermedo *et al.*, 2025).

A wide range of materials have been explored for emerging contaminants adsorption, including granular activated carbon, biochars, carbon nanotubes, metal oxides, and nanocomposites (Fallah *et al.*, n.d.; Ajiboye *et al.*, 2024; Adeoye *et al.*, 2024; Ahmad & Ejaz, 2023; Gautam *et al.*, 2024; Moreno-Bermedo *et al.*, 2025). Notably, BiFeO₃ nanoparticles and chitosan-based composites have shown high efficiency for drug removal (Abbasi *et al.*, 2021; Aminzai *et al.*, 2023). Functionalized and magnetic carbon materials have also demonstrated promising reuse potential (Adeoye *et al.*, 2024; Adel Naji & Tark Abd Ali, 2023).

Biological techniques include fungal and bacterial bioremediation, MBRs, sequencing batch reactors, and constructed wetlands (Chandran *et al.*, 2023; Alazaiza *et al.*, 2022; Bodle *et al.*, 2022; Hdidou *et al.*, 2022; Salvi-Taga *et al.*, 2024). Integration of adsorption with biological systems has improved the removal of various drugs (Chandran *et al.*, 2023).

AOPs, including Fenton, Photo-Fenton, and Electro-Fenton, have been extensively investigated for PPCPs and dye degradation (Abramov *et al.*, 2022;

Smulek *et al.*, 2021; Al-howri *et al.*, 2024; Adeoye *et al.*, 2024; Moreno-Bermedo *et al.*, 2025). Ozonation and photocatalysis are often coupled with other methods for enhanced efficiency (Hom-Diaz *et al.*, 2022; Ponce-Robles *et al.*, 2023). Electrode materials, such as modified biochar, have improved degradation rates in Electro-Fenton systems (Moreno-Bermedo *et al.*, 2025). Additional treatment approaches include coagulation/flocculation with natural coagulants, membrane filtration, and integrated AOP-biological processes for comprehensive contaminant removal (Alazaiza *et al.*, 2022; Miladi *et al.*, 2024; Pachaiappan *et al.*, 2022).

In closing, the chronological synthesis outlined in this section helps contextualize how scientific approaches to pharmaceutical pollution have advanced over time, offering a foundation for future innovation and policy development.

5 CONCLUSION

Pharmaceutical contamination in aquatic environments is intrinsically linked to local socioeconomic conditions. In regions with limited sanitation infrastructure, ineffective wastewater treatment systems, and inadequate regulatory frameworks, pharmaceuticals are more likely to persist in water sources. Research output in this field has grown significantly from 2000 to 2025, reflecting increased international collaboration, greater funding availability, and heightened awareness of the environmental and health implications of pharmaceutical pollutants. Funding agencies in China and Europe have dominated the financial landscape, with Brazilian institutions also playing a relevant role, indicating a strong geographical commitment to addressing this global issue. While high-income countries such as the United States and Germany lead in publication volume, developing economies like India and Brazil have also contributed substantially to the literature—often driven by internal policy incentives and the urgent need to ensure water quality for their populations.

From the full-text analysis of key publications, several recurring patterns and technological preferences were identified. The most common pharmaceutical pollutants include analgesics, anticonvulsants, antibiotics, and hormone-related compounds—many of which persist through conventional treatment. In response,

adsorption has emerged as the most widely studied approach, particularly using materials like activated carbon, biochar, carbon nanotubes, and metal oxides. Complementary strategies such as AOPs, membrane filtration, and biological systems (e.g., membrane bioreactors, constructed wetlands) have also gained traction. Recent advances point to a trend toward integration: combining treatment methods, employing nanomaterials, and applying modeling tools to enhance performance and scalability. These innovations reflect the field's interdisciplinary nature and underscore the need for efficient, adaptable solutions, especially in vulnerable regions where the health and environmental stakes are highest.

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